

DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' INTELLECTUAL COMPETENCE IN ENGLISH

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Abstract: *In the later stages of the development of the educational system, various new methods of teaching English are widely used. One of the important features of the communicative basis of teaching foreign languages is manifested in the systematic approach to the structural, functional and social aspects of the language. organizing, as well as improving the qualifications of teachers and providing them with modern educational and methodological materials is one of the main factors of further improvement.*

Key words: *listening comprehension, method, repetition, communication, challenges, goal, quick learning*

Students preparing for the IELTS exam face some language problems due to the characteristics of the English language. First of all, they prepare for the listening comprehension test for the exam. That is, students who are at the first stage of learning are the first to encounter the skill of listening and understanding. Therefore, it is appropriate to consider the difficulties in learning that may arise from the nature of the English language in terms of listening comprehension skills. we want to Although there is no question of solving these difficulties, overcoming them, taking into account the fact that familiarization with the difficulties of listening comprehension improves preparation for confusions and misunderstandings that may occur in the learning process, the following are the most we bring to your attention the difficulties noted by many learners:

1. PHONETIC DIFFICULTIES:

a) different sounds that are very similar to each other according to their acoustic properties (especially if there is no alternative to these sounds in the native language):...

- shortness and length of vowels;
- voiced or unvoiced consonants at the end of words;

b) acceptance of various expression images;

c) determining the interrelationship of meaningful groups or words.

2. LEXICAL DIFFICULTIES:

a) distinguish homonyms and homophones by listening;

b) distinguishing the meanings of ambiguous words;

c) to understand speech with unfamiliar words. In such a case, the test-taker will have to guess the translation of an unfamiliar word, or find out the translation according to the context (word formation, suffixes, international roots). Otherwise, it is necessary to ignore all unfamiliar words and draw a conclusion based on the general meaning of the sentence.

5 methods to quickly learn listening comprehension in English.

One of the most common questions I get about language learning is: "How can I learn English faster?" Therefore, in this article, I would like to give 5 tips on what to focus on when learning any language.

1. Define the goal clearly

Without a clear goal, it is impossible to achieve success in any work, especially in language learning. Therefore, think about what you want to learn English for. When I was a student, after studying, I taught English at a private language teaching center. The first lesson is always "Why do you want to study English?" I would start with a question. Unfortunately, more than half of the class could not say the exact purpose. There were many people who simply said, "My parents are sending it, it will be useful."

Since learning a language is a long and arduous process, a person who embarks on this path without a clear goal will never learn a language. On the contrary, the more serious your goal is, the faster and more effective language learning will be.

Everyone can set the goal based on their circumstances. For example, a school student can set a goal: "In two years, I will study English and enter the University of Westminster on a grant basis." A student may intend to "prepare for the TOEFL and enter an American university to study for a master's degree on the basis of a grant." A businessman can set a goal: "By learning English, I will learn new know-how related to my business and bring my company to the world market in 5 years."

Do not forget that the more serious the goal, the faster and more effective language learning will be.

2. Language is based on repetition

A language cannot be learned without constant repetition. You can memorize 10 new words a day, but if you don't repeat these words after 1-2 days, you will definitely forget them. One of the most effective ways is flash cards. Or, if not, you can effectively use the most eye-catching places. Personally, I used to write down the words I learned on a small piece of paper and stick them around my computer monitor and on my bedside table.

3. Communicate

Language is a means of communication. Therefore, in order to learn and develop a language, you naturally need to communicate. When I was a student, there were Speaking Clubs in various libraries and resource centers. Don't be afraid to participate even if you are not fluent yet. The one who tries to speak, even if he does not know the language better, wins than the one who is shy to participate in such conversations despite knowing the language. So, don't be shy, speak even with mistakes. Or, if not, find a partner to continue practicing English. Another advantage of learning a language with one or more partners is that this method creates a unique

competitive environment between partners. A neighbor or a classmate at school can be your partner. If you agree to learn at least 30 new words every week and meet on Sunday to test each other, you will definitely try to memorize the words so as not to fall behind your partner.

4. Adapt the language learning process to your lifestyle

Adapt the process of learning English to your lifestyle. For example, if you go to the university by subway every day, you will spend at least 30-40 minutes a day in the subway (counting 15-20 minutes each way). So, to make the most of your time on the subway, you can listen to various Listening Comprehension exercises (for example, Investudy English podcasts). Otherwise, when I was a student, classes were often canceled. This meant that I had to wait at least 1 hour for the next lesson. If you have similar situations, you can go to the library and spend this time only on things related to the English language. Otherwise, there is probably no one who does not watch movies of various genres. If you want to watch a movie, watch it in English with subtitles.

5. Use your smartphone effectively

Since learning a language is a long and arduous process, you should try to make it as easy as possible. Your smartphone will come in handy. There are free English learning programs that can be installed on smartphones. The most popular among them are Duolingo and Memrise. Duolingo and Memrise are similar. But the first noticeable difference is that in Duolingo, words are pronounced more in American English, and in Memrise in British English. Someone who knows a little English can listen to TED talks. After installing TED on your smartphone, you can listen to the conversation with subtitles if you select English subtitles in the Settings section. Learning English is not easy. This requires you to set a clear goal, keep repeating new words, communicate without shame when you have the opportunity, adapt the process of learning English to your life, and finally, use technology effectively.

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